

Possible Antiamoebic Agents. Part XVI

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Several 2-dialkylaminoalkylamino-pyridines and -pyrimidines have been prepared with a view to testing their antiamoebic activity.

It has been observed recently that many 2-di-(hydroxyalkyl)-aminopyridines (I) display antiamoebic activity *in vitro*¹. Substituted 2-aminopyrimidines and dipyrimidines (II) have also been found to possess antiamoebic activity².

The presence of one or two basic side chains at the position-2 is a noteworthy feature of these compounds. The *N*-dichloroacetylation of 2-pyridylmethylaminoethanols results in highly active amoebicides³. It is therefore considered that a similar *N*-dichloroacetylation of pyrimidines may also result in highly active amoebicides.

In the present investigation, several 2-dialkylaminoalkylamino-pyridines and -pyrimidines (with one or two basic side chains at position-2 in pyrimidine nucleus) as well as the *N*-dichloroacetanilidies of 2-dialkylaminoalkylaminopyrimidines have been prepared with a view to studying the effect of the number and length of the basic side chains and the effect of *N*-dichloroacetylation of pyrimidines on antiamoebic activity.

The desired 2-dialkylaminoalkylaminopyridines were obtained by the condensation of 2-chloro-5-nitropyridine with appropriate amine in ethanolic sodium acetate⁴. 2-Dialkylaminoalkylaminopyrimidines were prepared by the condensation of substituted 2-methylthiopyrimidines (0.1*M*) and appropriate amine (0.15*M*) at 170°; following the method of King and King⁵ the reaction took place with evolution of methylthiol and a gummy product was obtained which was purified by extraction with ethanol.

1. Neal and Vincent, *Brit. J. Pharm.*, 1955, 10, 434; Brown *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 1545.

2. Waletzky *et al.*, *Science*, 1950, 111, 720; Parnell, *Chem. Abst.*, 1961, 55, 6506.

3. Elalager *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 3453.

4. Mangini and Frenguelli, *Gazzetta*, 1939, 69, 88.

5. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 726.

2-(2-Hydroxyethyl-2-dialkylaminoethyl)-aminopyrimidines were obtained by the action of β -dialkylaminoethyl chloride on substituted 2-(2-hydroxyethyl)-aminopyrimidines in presence of sodamide in benzene.

N-Dichloroacetylation of substituted 2-(dialkylaminoalkyl)-aminopyrimidines was carried out in benzene solution. The pyridine and pyrimidine derivatives were characterised through their picrates.

EXPERIMENTAL

Dialkylaminoacetonitriles.—*N*-Cyanomethylpiperidine (yield 94%, b. p. 210°) and *N*-cyanomethyldiethylamine (yield 80%, b. p. 170°) were prepared by *N*-cyanomethylation of the corresponding secondary amines by the method of Luten.⁶

Dialkylaminopropionitriles were prepared by condensation of a secondary amine with acrylonitrile. Dimethylaminopropionitrile was prepared for the first time by adding in small portions with shaking and without external cooling 25% dimethylamine solution (10 ml) to acrylonitrile (10 g.) and allowing the mixture to stand overnight. Sufficient anhydrous potassium carbonate was then added to remove excess of water and the residual liquid was extracted with ether, dried over anhydrous potassium carbonate, and the nitrile isolated by distillation after removing the solvent; b. p. 171-72°, yield 86%. (Found: N, 28.32. Calc. N: 28.57%). Picrate m. p. 155°. (Found: N, 21.50. Calc. N: 21.40%). Diethylaminopropionitrile (b. p. 195-96°, yield 92%), piperidinepropionitrile (b. p. 220-22°, yield 90%), morpholinopropionitrile (b. p. 244-46°, yield 90%) were prepared by the method of Whitmore *et al.*⁷

Reduction of nitriles to amines was effected in excellent yields with Raney nickel T-1⁸ in slightly alkaline conditions as follows.

A mixture of the appropriate nitrile (0.1 *M*), sodium ethoxide (0.1 g.), and Raney nickel T-1 (1-1.5g.) in absolute ethanol (50 ml) was hydrogenated at room temperature at 60 lbs./p.s.i. in a Parr hydrogenation apparatus for 5 hours. The absorption was practically complete within 2 hours. It was filtered and the amines isolated as usual: β -piperidinoethylamine, b. p. 184°, yield 70%; β -diethylaminoethylamine, b. p. 145°, yield 65%; γ -dimethylaminopropylamine, b. p. 125-26°, yield 65% (% N found: 27.50; calc. 27.45%; picrate m. p. 220°; % N found: 19.80; calc. 19.93%); γ -diethylaminopropylamine, b. p. 168°, yield 78%; γ -piperidinopropylamine, b. p. 202-204°, yield 85%; γ -morpholinopropylamine, b. p. 216-18°, yield 88%.

2-Chloro-5-nitropyridine was prepared by the method of Caldwell⁹.

Substituted Pyrimidines.—4-Methyl-2-thiouracil was prepared by a quick procedure as follows: Ethyl acetoacetate (13 g.) and thiourea (18 g.) were added with shaking to sodium ethoxide (from 3 g. sodium and 50 ml absolute ethanol). It was kept at 50° for 1 hour and

6. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1939, **3**, 598.

7. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, **66**, 727.

8. Dominguez *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **26**, 1625.

9. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **64**, 1690.

then refluxed on a water bath for 2 hours; excess of ethanol was then removed by distillation. The solid obtained was dissolved in water and acidified with acetic acid. The precipitate obtained thus was filtered, washed with cold water, and finally recrystallised from acetic acid. It was almost a pure compound, which did not melt when heated to 270°; yield 95%. (Found: N, 19.96. Calc. N: 19.71%). List¹⁰ reports m.p. >280°.

4-Methyl-2-methylthiouracil.—The above thiouracil (14.4 g.) in aqueous sodium carbonate (11 g. in 200 ml) was shaken at room temperature with dimethyl sulphate (10 ml) for 2 hours. The solid separating was collected and washed successively with water, ethanol, and ether. It was dried in a vacuum desiccator. It was sufficiently pure to be used in the next step; m.p. 217-19°, yield 10 g. List¹¹ reports m. p. 220°.

2-Thiobarbituric acid was prepared by a known method¹².

2-Methylthiobarbituric acid was prepared according to King and King⁵.

2-Dialkylaminopropylamino-5 nitropyridines.—2-Chloro-5-nitropyridine, the appropriate amine, and fused sodium acetate (0.1 M, each) were refluxed in absolute ethanol (50 ml) for 4 hours on a water bath. The solution was then filtered hot. On cooling, yellow needles separated which were filtered and heated at 90° for some time to remove any 2-chloro-5-nitropyridine. It was finally recrystallised from ethanol.

The picrates of these were obtained in the usual way from ethanol. The m.p.'s, %yields, and analyses of the dialkylaminoalkylpyridines and their picrates are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

No.	-N $\begin{matrix} \diagup R' \\ \diagdown R' \end{matrix}$	%Yield.	*M.P.	%Nitrogen.		Picrates		
				Found.	Reqd.	M.P.	%Nitrogen. Found.	Reqd.
1	-NMe ₂	70	64°	25.06	25.00	..	..	..
2	-NEt ₂	72	78-80°	22.30	22.22	..	..	..
3		70	80-82°	21.25	21.21	195°	18.50	18.56
4		75	102°	21.12	21.05	112°	18.42	18.51

*All compounds are hygroscopic. M. P. determined in sealed capillary tubes.

10. List, *Annalen*, 1886, 236, 6.

11. List, *ibid.*, p. 12.

12. Michael, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1894, 49, 38.

TABLE II

No.	R'	R''	%Yield.	M.P.	%Nitrogen.		Purposes.		Found.	Reqd.
					Found.	Reqd.	M.P.	Formula.		
1	Me	Ph	55	> 250°	19.42	19.53	190°	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₆	18.82	18.91
2	OH	"	45	> 250°	19.38	19.43	204°	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₆	18.80	18.83
3	Me	-OH	95	190°	25.32	25.44	194°	C ₁₃ H ₄ O ₂ N ₆	20.90	21.10
4	OH	"	80	172°	24.30	24.56	174°	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₁₀ N ₆	20.90	21.00
5	Me		75	> 240°	23.61	23.72	175°	C ₁₆ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₇	21.16	21.07
6	"	-NEt ₂	80	> 250°	25.18	25.00	244°	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₇	23.20	23.09
7	"	-NMe ₂	65	68°	26.70	26.66	178°	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₇	22.51	22.42
8	"	-NEt ₂	70	70°	23.41	23.52	189°	C ₁₆ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₇	21.18	21.07
9	"		80	75°	22.21	22.40	210°	C ₁₆ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₇	20.57	20.54
10	"		75	98°	22.26	22.22	218°	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₇	20.58	20.50

2-Dialkylaminoalkylaminopyrimidines were obtained by heating substituted 2-methylthiopyrimidines (0.1M) and appropriate amine (0.15 M) at 170° (CaCl₂-guard tube) till the evolution of methylthiol ceased (ca. 30 min.). The reaction mixture was cooled, the product extracted with ethanol, treated with charcoal, and filtered again. From the filtrate ethanol was distilled under suction and the gummy mass, thus obtained, was recrystallised from ethanol-acetone or ethanol-benzene. The picrates of these were prepared as usual from ethanol. The m.p.'s, %yields, and analyses of the pyrimidines and their picrates are recorded in Table II.

Dichloroacetyl chloride was prepared by the method of Brown¹³; b.p. 111°, yield 70%.

N-Dichloroacetanilides of 2-dialkylaminoalkylaminopyrimidines were prepared in benzene solution. To a solution of appropriate pyrimidine (0.15 M) in dry thiophene-free benzene (25 ml) was added dichloroacetyl chloride (0.30 M) with shaking. An exothermic reaction occurred. After keeping for 20 mins. the mixture was washed with 1% sodium bicarbonate solution (20 ml) and then with water; it was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the benzene distilled. The solid was collected and recrystallised from dimethylformamide. The m.p.'s, % yields, and analyses of these are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

No.	n.	R.	%Yield.	M.P.	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.
1	1	Ph	40	190°	12.70	12.82
2	2	OH	55	172°	10.40	10.50
3	2		58	134°	16.00	16.13
4	3	-NEt ₂	60	84°	15.94	16.04
5	3		58	98°	15.38	15.48
6	3		62	86°	15.43	15.51

N-Dialkylaminoethanols.—*N*-Piperidinoethanol (b.p. 199°) and *N*-diethylaminoethanol (b.p. 161°) were prepared according to Ladenberg¹⁴, and *N*-morpholinoethanol (b.p. 219-20°) according to Cumming *et al*.¹⁵

N-Dialkylaminoethyl Chloride Hydrochlorides.—The above alcohols were treated with thionyl chloride in thiophene-free benzene to yield the corresponding chloride hydrochlorides: *N*-piperidinoethyl chloride hydrochloride, m.p. 228°; *N*-morpholinoethyl chloride hydrochloride, m.p. 180; *N*-diethylaminoethyl chloride hydrochloride¹⁶, m.p. 205°.

2-(2-Hydroxyethyl-2-dialkylaminoethyl)-amincyrimidines.—2-(2-Hydroxyethyl)-amino-4-methyluracil (0.3 *M*), dry thiophene-free benzene (50 ml) and sodamide (0.3 *M*) were refluxed on a water-bath for 1 hour and then *N*-dialkylaminoethyl chloride hydrochloride (10.15*M*) was added. It was refluxed for 8 hours on a water-bath; it was then washed with aq. K₂CO₃, dried (Na₂SO₄), benzene removed, and the resulting solid was recrystallised from ethanol-acetone. The m.p.'s, %yields, and analyses of these are recorded in Table IV.

TABLE IV

No.	R'	R''	% Yield.	M.P.	% Nitrogen.	
					Found	Reqd.
1	OH	OH	50	181°	19.40	19.53
2	Me	„	50	> 270°	19.62	19.71
3	„	-NEt ₂ ^a	55	198°	20.81	20.89
4	„	-N	60	204°	20.09	20.00
5	„	-N	60	217°	19.71	19.85

^aCompounds are hygroscopic.

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14. *Ber.*, 1881, 14, 1877

15. *Chem., Abst.*, 1940, 34, 4388.

16. Bartlett *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 1416.